

Substituent Effects in the Oxidation of Benzaldehyde by Ce^{4+}

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The reaction between benzaldehyde and Ce^{4+} in H_2SO_4 -HOAc mixtures in N_2 atmosphere was found to obey a second order rate law. There was no evidence for complex formation between Ce^{4+} and C_6H_5CHO . The effect of substituent on the rate was determined by using C_6H_5CHO and five substituted derivatives. The Hammett's plot was found to be linear with a slope equal to -0.59 . The order of reactivity of the substituents was $p-CH_3 > H > p-Cl > m-Cl > m-NO_2 > p-NO_2$.

IN the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by chromic acid¹ the electron withdrawing substituents increased the rate and the order of reactivity reported was :

A similar trend was observed when² Mn^{3+} and³ Co^{3+} were employed as oxidants. However, in the oxidation of benzaldehyde by Ce^{4+} in $HClO_4$ and HOAc mixture, Wiberg and Ford⁴ found that the substituents attached to the phenyl ring retarded the rate of oxidation regardless of the sign of the Hammett's σ value. In this paper we present the data on the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by Ce^{4+} in H_2SO_4 -HOAc mixture wherein a different trend of reactivity was observed.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either BDH (AR) grade or were purified adopting standard procedures. The method of following the reaction was the same as in our earlier paper⁵.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be 2 moles of Ce^{4+} to one mole of $X-C_6H_5CHO$ and the product was identified as $X-C_6H_5COOH$. The aldehyde and ceric solutions were thoroughly flushed with N_2 before mixing since, oxygen was found to have a marked effect on the reaction rate. The order of $[Ce^{4+}]$ and $[C_6H_5CHO]$ was one each and the overall order

was two as seen from the plot of $\frac{1}{a-x}$ vs time (Fig. 1A)

which was linear for over seventy per cent of the reaction when equal concentrations of aldehyde and Ce^{4+} were used. Increase in percentage of acetic acid decreased the rate from $k' = 5.10 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ (20% HOAc) to $3.79 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ (60% HOAc). The plot of $\log k$ vs σ was linear with a slope (ρ) of -0.59 (Fig. 1B). The kinetic studies were carried out in 85% v/v aqueous acetic acid since this mixture gave a convenient rate of reaction and is similar to that used in

Figure 1

(A) Plot of $P \frac{1}{a-x}$ vs time

(Ce^{4+}) = 0.00525 M ; (C_6H_5CHO) = 0.00525 M ; temp = 50°
(H_2SO_4) = 1.45 M ; μ = 4.60 M ; (HOAc) = 85% v/v.

(B) Plot of $\log k' + 2$ vs σ

Conditions same as in (A) for the various substituted benzaldehydes.

synthetic work. Further, above this percentage ceric acetate polymers precipitated and below it the solubility of aldehydes presented a big problem. From the solvent effect studies on the kinetics of oxidation of a variety of organic substrates by Ce^{4+} in H_2SO_4 -HOAc mixtures the active species was proved to be neutral ceric sulphate $Ce(SO_4)_2$ molecule⁶. The type of mechanism suggested for the oxidation of benzaldehydes by Ce^{4+} in $HClO_4$ medium involving complex formation between Ce^{4+} and C_6H_5CHO which later dissociated in the rate determining step is ruled out in

H₂SO₄ - HOAc mixtures as Ce(SO₄)₂ molecule resists further complexation⁶ and also the plot of 1/k' vs $\frac{1}{[C_6H_5CHO]}$ (where k' is the observed pseudo first order rate constant under conditions $[C_6H_5CHO] \gg [Ce^{4+}]$) was linear passing through the origin (fig. 2A).

Figure 2

(A) Plot of $\frac{1}{k'}$ vs $\frac{1}{[C_6H_5CHO]}$

(Ce⁴⁺) = 0.008 M ; (H₂SO₄) = 1.0 M ; temp = 42°
(HOAc) = 60% v/v ; μ = 3.1 M.

(B) Plot of ΔH[‡] vs -ΔS[‡]
isokinetic temperature β = 330°K.

However, at higher concentrations of Ce⁴⁺ and C₆H₅CHO a slight intensification of colour, probably due to complex formation, was no doubt noticed but the rate was too fast to be followed under those conditions. Since e⁴⁺ is a one electron abstractor the first step should involve the formation of a free radical. This could be due to the fission of the C-H bond. The probable mechanism could be written as :

The rate equation from the above scheme comes out as :

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{4+}]}{dt} = k [Ce^{4+}] [C_6H_5CHO] \quad (4)$$

That the second step is faster is obvious since it involves free radicals. The above mechanism explains both the stoichiometry and the experimentally observed rate law. The presence of free radicals was confirmed by the induced polymerisation of acrylamide. The increase in rate with increase in percentage of acetic acid in HClO₄ medium was attributed by Wiberg and Ford¹ to the ion-dipole type of reaction occurring. In the present study, the decrease in rate with increasing acetic acid indicates probably the neutral Ce(SO₄)₂ is reactive and the reaction in H₂SO₄ medium is a dipole-dipole type one.

The effect of substituents on the rate of reaction was determined using benzaldehyde and five substituted derivatives. The rate constants and other thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 1.

The plot of log k vs σ gives a straight line with a correlation coefficient 0.987. Although some reactions involving radicals are correlated better by σ⁻ and some by σ⁺ for our purpose the distinction is not critical. Since Ce⁴⁺ system is electrophilic and is expected to induce an electron deficient centre in the transition state the ρ value of -0.59 (Fig. 1B) obtained in this present study is in accordance with other radical processes which are normally between⁷ -0.5 and -1.5. Further, since both meta and para substituents fit into the above plots the resonance effect of the para substituent is probably negligible. The rates of oxidation for various substituents are in the order p-CH₃ > H > p-Cl > m-Cl > m-NO₂ > p-NO₂. The plot of ΔH[‡] vs ΔS[‡] was linear with a slope equal to 330° (Fig. 2B) which is the isokinetic temperature. The temperature

TABLE 1.—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR CERIC SULPHATE-BENZALDEHYDE REACTIONS

S. No.	Substrate	k'' × 10 ² l mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ at 55°	ΔE [‡] k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔG [‡] k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] e. u.
1	p-CH ₃	11.75	19.40	18.75	20.65	- 5.79
2	H	10.66	19.20	18.55	20.73	- 6.65
3	p-Cl	7.28	15.60	14.95	20.56	-17.10
4	m-Cl	6.58	19.23	18.58	21.04	- 7.50
5	m-NO ₂	3.60	20.37	19.72	21.43	- 5.21
6	p-NO ₂	3.51	13.70	13.05	21.45	-25.61

range used for the study of these reactions was from 313° to 331°K. The nearness of the experimental temperature to the isokinetic temperature is probably the reason for the small effect of the substituents observed. The linear relationship between $\Delta S^\ddagger$ and $\Delta H^\ddagger$ can be fitted into the equation $\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$.

$\Delta H_0^\ddagger$ has a value of 20.6 K cal mol⁻¹. This linear relationship shown by a majority of the substituted benzaldehydes indicate that apparently the same mechanism prevails in all the cases.

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